

To develop children's interest in visual art, their outlook on art

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Abstract. Knowledge of drawing is necessary not only for artists, designers, architects, but also for teachers, engineers, doctors, builders, agronomists, soldiers, and scientists. The schools are called general secondary education schools according to their name, and have the task of providing children with general, elementary knowledge and skills in fine, practical and architectural arts, among other subjects. It should also be noted that general secondary education schools do not train artists, do not envisage working with talented children and developing them.

Key words: Picture, knowledge, artist, designer, architect, teacher, school, education, children, science, fine art, knowledge.

The purpose of the subject of visual arts in general secondary education schools is focused on the formation of the artistic culture of a well-rounded, perfect person.

The subject of visual arts provides basic knowledge and skills of artistic culture, which are necessary for every person. Because every student, regardless of what field he will work in the future, he will have to rest, relax, and restore the energy spent during work. He achieves this by getting acquainted with works of art made at a high artistic level in museums, exhibitions and other places, perceiving them and enjoying them. Students will have to make a certain amount of paintings in their future life.

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Training of artists, work with talented children is carried out in school clubs, special schools and academic lyceums, colleges and universities. It is not correct to try to give tasks that lead to

When we talk about the tasks of visual art classes at school, they can be conditionally divided into two parts.

1. The special tasks of fine arts classes are:

teaching to see, perceive, understand and appreciate the beauties of existence and art; development of aesthetic and artistic taste; expanding children's range of artistic thought; development of artistic creativity and imagination; to introduce the theoretical foundations of fine art (light, shadow, color science, perspective, composition); formation of elements and skills related to painting, sculpting, artistic construction; development of observation, visual memory, ability to guess, spatial and image perception, abstract and logical thinking; teaching to read and understand visual and practical architectural works of art; arousing interest in art, teaching to appreciate and love it.

2. Additional duties of fine arts teachers, they are; help to know the rest, life; implementation of the ideology of national pride and national independence; moral to children (patriotic, international); implementation of work, physical education; sending children to various professions and trades.

When talking about the purpose and tasks of the visual arts subject, it should be noted that it is connected with almost all subjects taught at school and has an effective effect on mastering the materials related to them. . It is especially important in reading, literature,

geography, natural science, biology, history, mathematics, and labor lessons. Visual arts are useful even for physical education, chemistry, and music classes. It should also be noted that fine art is aimed at the implementation of aesthetic education, but it also serves to increase the effectiveness of moral, labor, environmental, and physical education classes.

Fine art is considered the main educational subject aimed at the implementation of aesthetic education in the school, and it is implemented in the following directions:

- teaching students to perceive the beauties of nature, art and life:
- education of students' aesthetic taste, ability to appreciate beauty, teaching to distinguish real beauty from ugly events and things;
- to develop the skills to show oneself in the visual and creative activities of a person, to support one's behavior and to add beauty to life:
- expanding children's range of artistic thinking, etc.

According to its nature, the subject of fine art education is important in developing such qualities as aesthetic perception, aesthetic pleasure, aesthetic feeling, aesthetic taste, aesthetic judgment, aesthetic evaluation, aesthetic creativity, which are the basis of aesthetic education. plays a role. In decorative composition classes, students feel the beauty of patterns and practical art objects and try to create such compositions themselves.

Students are excited by the bright and shiny, elegant and clean nature of things, the return or exchange of their parts, and their symmetrical arrangement. The variety of colors and shapes of flowers in nature, butterflies and dragonflies, the light makeup of birds, the beauty of spring and autumn landscapes, the lushness of willows, the glistening of lawns under the sunlight, and the evening flickering of house windows are exciting. The growth of such a feeling in children leads to the formation of the skills of aesthetic evaluation of the properties of objects and events. The use of figurative expressions in children's activities, i.e. "good mood", "joyful", "like on a holiday" indicates that they are developing the skills of aesthetic perception of existence and events.

By showing the branches and leaves of the trees, the teacher notes that the young leaves are light-green and delicate in color. emphasizes that the grains of iron look like silver. In nature in the autumn season, the yellow and red colors of tree leaves have become golden, and the rustling "talking" of fallen leaves is figuratively expressed.

Children depict houses, trees, birds, animals, people, vehicles in their pictures. From this, they face the dimensions, proportions, texture, shapes, and colors of the subjects without words and try to place them correctly in the picture compositionally. This encourages us to think about the proportionality, perfection, appropriateness of their structure. Children think about the aspects of objects and animals that attract them in terms of shape and color, from which side they look beautiful, and what are their good and useful aspects. As the students think about things and events in nature, the teacher focuses on the beauty and perfection of the events and events that match their understanding. Through beauty experiences, he tries to teach children to appreciate the surrounding phenomena and events, awakens feelings of humanity, love for the country, passion for work.

Fine art helps children to know existence and life. Before starting to draw pictures of things and events, they study the structure, shape, dimensions, color, and spatial conditions of things and describe them in their work. They also get an idea about the life of the observed living things, as a result, the children's imagination about the world deepens and expands, and their memories develop.

On the basis of observation of historical, batal genre paintings of fine art, illustrations used in literary works, children will learn about the lifestyle, culture, clothing, and working tools of our ancestors who lived thousands of years ago. They will have an idea about the structure, shape, color, dimensions of buildings, plants, animals, objects of that period. It is known that children will have a lot of knowledge about historical events, battles, people's lives, animals, urban and natural landscapes in the paintings that work in historical, battle, landscape, life, still life, animal, legendary genres.

In the process of teaching fine arts, the tasks set allow students to show their individuality and intellectual abilities one by one. Children encourage themselves to be creative when solving educational tasks. They are not able to solve the problem quickly and easily in a way that is already known to the creator, but they use their creativity and imagination, the qualities of moderation and harmony through new, irreversible solutions to the problem. As a result, a certain amount of original, new, irrevocable creative product is born.

Creativity, creative thinking persons are not simple performers, they are the main force that develops society. That is why our society needs thinking, inquisitive, creative, initiative people, not robot-like performers. The development of our society largely depends on such people. Thinking, inquisitive, creative people in our society who can quickly and easily find a solution to any unforeseen situation in our society will raise the development of our nation to new levels.

Creative thinking gives rise to completely new ideas and imaginations, helps to realize hidden abilities and opportunities, individuality. It should be noted that such qualities are important not only for scientists, but also for workers in all fields (engineers, doctors, farmers, bakers, etc.).

The subject of visual arts is not only important in the aesthetic education of young people, but also occupies an important place in moral education. Especially, visual art classes have a great power in forming the ideology of national independence, in patriotism and international education, in forming the ideas of friendship and mutual assistance among young people. Looking at the visual arts program of the school, it is full of visual art works that express the great past of our country, the struggle of our compatriots for independence, the refined nature of Uzbekistan, and the ideas of friendship between peoples. we will be the witness of the overflow.

In today's conditions, where the scale of necessary knowledge for a person is expanding, it is impossible to limit yourself to the acquisition of a certain set of facts. Therefore, it is necessary to teach students to fill and enrich their knowledge independently, to focus their attention on the most important scientific and political information. This task requires the expansion and development of students' visual art lessons in a way that is integrally connected with the educational process.

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